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Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom

Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed¹

Kālidāsa is a celebrated classical Sanskrit writer of ancient India, travelling through the romantic poetic universe with a different perspective. He mainly contributes three notable plays and two great poems as a poet and dramatist. *Meghasandēśa* is his messenger poem that started the message movement in Indian Literature. *Ṛitusamhāra* also belongs to him, and he portrays six seasons fantastically. *Kālidāsa*, who fully understood Vedic knowledge, gave place to Vedāntic insight in his poems. He was proficient in all philosophical traditions of ancient India and adopted a stimulating method; many complicated subjects in ancient thought were simplified. Kālidāsa was also a pioneer in the Vedānta tradition of ancient India. Many non-dualistic and dualistic thoughts of ancient traditions can be seen in his works, which were severe thoughts of the realm of Classical Indian philosophy. This paper mainly analyses Vedānta's thoughts, including classical Vedānta traditions, which Kālidāsa illustrated.

Having a clear view of the Vedic system, Kālidāsa seems to have integrated Vedic traditions, and *Upaniṣad*-ic thought in all his works. The *Upaniṣad*-s, a collection of ancient texts, are closely related to the Vedānta philosophy. Vedānta, which means the end of the *Veda*-s, is a school of Hindu philosophy that interprets the *Upaniṣad*-s. It later evolved into such philosophies as Advaita, Viśiṣṭadvaita, and Dvaita, each with its unique interpretation of the *Upaniṣad*-s. Many

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of the significant principles mentioned in the ancient Vedānta philosophies, and later in the classical Vedānta, such as Advaita, Viśiṣṭādvaita, and Dvaita, appear to be in sync with the Kālidāsa literature. Kālidāsa and the classical philosophers have assimilated many valuable concepts from ancient Vedānta thought. During the period of Śankara, classical Advaita flourished at a higher level. The *Upaniṣad-s* and the *Brahmasūtra* of Badarayana are the influential texts of Vedānta tradition in ancient India. The primary texts of the classical Vedānta system are the commentaries on the *Brahmasūtra*, the *Upaniṣad-s*, and the *Bhagavadgītā*. Kālidāsa assimilated ancient Vedānta thoughts into his works. Kālidāsa took a different approach than the classical Vedānta thinkers when he incorporated the Vedānta thoughts into his literary series. However, many of the classical Vedānta thoughts interact with Kālidāsa's thoughts.

As mentioned earlier, Kālidāsa systematically harmonised the great thoughts from ancient texts and conveyed them with a simple and unique style. Despite the *Veda-s* containing a multitude of gods and goddesses, the inclination to elevate the primary gods to the mainstream was a characteristic of early Indian thought. Kālidāsa, who had embraced the Vedic system, utilised the trinity concept in his works. The tenth canto of the *Raghuvamśā* extols *Brahma* with profound reverence. In contrast, the second canto of the *Kumārasaṃbhava* expresses a deep respect for *Brahma*, and Lord *Viṣṇu* makes an appearance in the eleventh canto of the same. Similar to the Advaita tradition, the *Brahman* concept is vividly described by Kālidāsa in *Kumārasaṃbhava*. The broader vision of Vedānta, i.e., 'Sarvam Khalvidam Brahman' and the Ṛigvedic phrase 'Ekamsadviprabahudavadanthi', are significantly influenced by Kālidāsa's literature. This influence underscores the profound impact of Kālidāsa's work on the broader vision of Vedānta in ancient India, highlighting the depth of his spiritual exploration and the reverence for *Brahma* in his works.

Śankara, the great scholar of Advaita, regards *Brahman* as the ultimate reality of the universe. He also accepts the three kinds of realities (*sattatraya-s*): empirical, illusionary, and transcendental, while the last is the ultimate and everlasting one. He reminds us that the last is the state of realisation of *Brahman*, which is omniscient,

omnipresent, and everlasting. According to Śankara, *Brahman* is eternal, pure, liberated, knowledgeable and assertive. He defined *Brahman* as *nityaśuddhamuktasarvañamsarvaśaktisamanvitam* (*Adhyāśabhāṣya* of *Brahmasūtra*). When one realises *Brahman*'s existence in oneself, other realities exist in that person. Then, the reality of the empirical world will be similar to the dreamlike manifestation of reality. Śankara explains that *Brahman* is the basis for all phenomena in nature. He explains the inseparability of *Ātman* and *Brahman* through the aphorism *brahmavidbrahmaivabhavati*. With the acquisition of transcendental knowledge of *Brahman*, he loses phenomenal existence when he attains the knowledge of *Brahman* as one who knows actual knowledge of rope instead of a snake. The creation process of the empirical things described by Kālidāsa in *Kumārasambhava* is similar to the material reality described by Śankara in Advaita. It shows Kālidāsa's strong influence on the philosophers of ancient India is evident here. The soul is created by a principle that identifies the soul with itself. To this soul, every person attains value after the act of karma (*Kumārasambhava* 2.10). Ancient scholars of Vedānta have re-invented the principles of *Ātman* and *Brahman* enunciated in the *Veda*-s and *Upaniṣad*-s in different ways. Śankara adopted a different exposition style to explain the unity of *Brahman* and *Ātman* from that adopted by Gaudapāda in *Mandūkyakārika*. The root forms of *parabrahman* and *aparabrahman* can also be seen in the *Rigveda*.

Kālidāsa describes God in *Raghuvamśā* as the ultimate reality of the universe. He is the knower of all things in the world. He knows everything but does not know his source. This principle is derived from it; nothing is more than that oneness (*Raghuvamśā* 10.20). In Another instance, Kālidāsa reminds us that a non-dual creation is the cause of the universe, though it resembles the Sāṅkhya of Sage Kapila, a prominent figure in Indian philosophy. The Sāṅkhya philosophy, attributed to Sage Kapila, is one of the six major schools of Indian philosophy and is known for its dualistic view of the universe. It shows that the fundamental cause of the creation of the universe is an obscure principle. This ambiguity is the limitless principle found in the finite physical universe. No one can conquer this principle, which does not require prayer in a prayerful world.

This principle, which is the fundamental cause of the creation of the universe, conquers all (*Raghuvamśā* 10.18).

What is the real sense of Śankara's aphorism '*brahma vid brahmaivabhavati*'? The answer is straightforward, i.e., those who know *Brahman* become *Brahman*. He adds that two things with unique qualities behave like truth and darkness (*Satyānrita*). Thus, the practical universe exists without recognising the oneness of the soul. Ignorance is the universe's cause, like the knowledge of a snake instead of a rope. In *Kumārasaṃbhava*, Kālidāsa accepts the oneness of the soul and says that we honour the spirit that came from you; belief becomes the respect of one's qualities (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 6.20). Kālidāsa's view, based on the sense of unity of the soul, resonates with that of Śankara. The aphorism '*Sarvamkhalvidambrahma*' is quoted by Śankara to justify the universe's actual cause, which is equally possible to accept Kālidāsa in *Kumārasaṃbhava*. God (*Jagadīswara*) is the ultimate cause of the world. It is the cause of distraction in the universe and has no beginning or end. *Nirīwara* (Godless) is the ultimate cause of the universe (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 2.9).

In Advaita, *ātman* and *Brahman* are the same. Due to ignorance, nobody knows the fundamental nature of the *Brahman*. In the preface of the *Brahmasūtra* commentary, Śankara points out that the soul's intimate relationship with Brahman is made clear. It shows Śankara's skill more than other scholars of Vedānta in his period. He interprets a different view in his philosophy to explain his great thought of non-dualism. He prompts that illusionary knowledge is an excellent obstacle to ultimate reality. He used *adhyāsa* to denote ignorance, which is defined in two ways: one is '*atasmin tadbuddhiradhyāsa*', and another is '*smṛtirūpaḥ paratra pūrvadrṣṭāvabhāsa*'. It is a true reflection of reality. The remembrance of the previous object in the apparent object gives the knowledge of reality, which is the meaning of first. The second interpretation is the production of natural intelligence, which occurs in this way in an unreal object. These two interpretations given in this study prove the existence of one thing in another that differs from it.

Śankara uses worldly examples such as śuki-rajatam and the chariot seen in a dream to prove the non-existence of empirical reality. Kālidāsa makes a very complex application of the metaphysical

thoughts of the Advaitin-s in technical terms such as *māya* and *avidya* instead of ignorance. In *Kumārasaṃbhava*, Kālidāsa uses the word *dhvāntam* (*tama*:) instead of *adhyāsa*. It explains that he (Śiva), who was not affected by *avidya* (darkness) and was like the moonlight, sang the *Tripuravijaya katha* by Viswvasu, who was great at playing the *vīṇa*. The word *dhvāntam* here refers to ignorance. Kālidāsa recalls that those who should be mentioned as *Brahmadi*-s accompanied Viśvasu, who sang the *Tripuravijaya katha*, which was untouched by ignorance and praised by the world (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 7.48).

Śāstrayonitvād is one of the aphorisms in *Brahmasūtra*, and Śankara interprets it in a different style. He accepts a simple way to interpret it. He describes *Brahman* as the source of the *Veda*-s; later, he describes that *Brahman* is not known from any other source. In *Kumārasaṃbhava*, Kālidāsa brings forth an equivalent and unwavering strength in tune with Śankara's vision. That is the cause of the *Veda*. The nature of *Veda* is enquiring later. The beginning is with *Omkāra*, and the pronunciation is harmonious with the *udātta*, *anudātta*, and *swarita*. The knowledge of *Veda* is the result that is the attainment of heaven. Knowledge is the path that leads everyone to the ultimate goal (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 2.12). The *Kumārasaṃbhava* also reminds us that *havyam* and *bhogyā* (result) are the same. That one is the eternal knower and the consumer (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 2.15). Kālidāsa also agrees with the aphorism of *Upaniṣad*-s like *Brahmavidbrahmaivabhavati*, similar to Kālidāsa's feelings with Vedānta's thoughts.

In Advaita, those who have attained the ultimate truth (*Brahmasiddhi*) never return to the previous state of life. Śankara does not deny the existence of empirical reality. In *Kumārasaṃbhava*, Kālidāsa reminds us that the beginning of the worship comes from the *Brahman*, whom the *Veda*-s mentioned. It is the only one that is divided into three (*mūrttitraya*). It is generally discussed here as to who is in front of whom. In some places, Hari stands before Hara. In another instance, Hara stands before Hari. In another context, *Brahman* is situated in front of Hari and Viṣṇu (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 7.44).

Kālidāsa presents the unique reason for the creation of the

universe in *Raghuvamśa* in a straightforward way. The first thing to do is create the universe, while its existence and destruction must occur in subsequent stages (*Raghuvamśā* 10.16). The poet here reminds us of an essential principle responsible for all three changes in worldly phenomena. *Kumārasaṃbhava* witnesses Kālidāsa's acceptance of *Nirguṇabrahman*, one of Śankara's most significant concepts. The inactive (*nirguṇa*) and formless (*niravayava*) self is the root cause of the universe, where qualities like *sattva*, *raja*, and *tama* combine to create diversified resources (*Kumārasaṃbhava* 2.4). Paying homage to this unique idol of diversity, Kālidāsa highlights the greatness of the Vedic tradition there.

Having accepted the empirical reality, Śankara has adopted precise methods to establish the existence of worldly phenomena. Kālidāsa also makes it clear that no one can accurately determine your (Śiva) greatness, even with verbal testimony and inference, and the only means of recognising your validity are the precepts of the maxim and the conjecture (*Raghuvamśā* 10.28). The poet here recalls the unique place given to the verbal testimony (*śabda*) in the *pramānaśāstra* to identify the non-quality and formless *Brahman*.

Rāmānuja and Madhvā were among the foremost critics of the Advaita doctrine. They also wrote commentaries on the *Brahmasūtra*, the *Upaniṣad-s*, and the *Bhagavadgītā* and stated that *Saguṇabrahma* (Brahman with quality) is the fundamental principle of the universe. Śankara interpreted the aphorism *ekamevādvītyam* as *Brahman*, which is one and unique. Rāmānuja, who interpreted the same verse in *Śrībhāshya*, explained that the universe's properties are unique. Rāmānuja, the devotee of Viṣṇu, places the Divine God in Brahman's place. He explains that *citacitvīśistaśvara* is the ultimate cause of the universe. Madhvā, the chief exponent of the dualist philosopher of ancient India, explains in his commentary that the Lord of all things in nature is *Brahman* with all-knowing qualities. There are five kinds of reality in everything. They are God and the living entities, God and the material objects, the living entities and the material objects, the one living entity and the other living entity, the material objects and the other material objects. The world is a combination of whole things. Just as *Brahman* is real, so is the nature of the five senses. This diversity is due to the diversity and diversity in nature.

Kālidāsa, who dealt with the royal and court experiences of ancient India from the perspective of a historian, dealt with the characters like *Brahma*, *Viṣṇu*, *Śiva*, Daśaratha, and Rāma mentioned in the *Veda*-s and *Purāṇa*-s without harming their divine nature. Kālidāsa's Praise of *Viṣṇu* in the tenth canto of *Raghuvamśā* is similar to Ramanuja's remembrance of *Viṣṇu*, who adopted the devotional path. Kālidāsa reveals how the ocean's jewels are like the sunrise; in the same way, your activities, different from the usual, are full of Praise (*Raghuvamśā* 10.30).

Kālidāsa's devotional discourses converse so much with Rāmānuja's, who argued that *karma* and *bhakti* are the sources of knowledge. *Viṣṇu* is also seen in the tenth canto of *Raghuvamśā*. The gods were pleased with *Viṣṇu*. It was never a compliment because that Praise was absolute for *Viṣṇu* (*Raghuvamśā* 10.33).

The tenth canto of *Raghuvamśā* shares a definite position that explains the role of *Brahman* in the creation of the universe. Wisdom is the fruit of four *puruṣārthā*-s. Different phenomena occur in nature according to the variations of the four *yugā*-s. The combination of the four *varṇā*-s (*cāturvarṇyā*) is the reason for the diversity in the universe. All the worldly phenomena emanate from the four-faced *Brahman* (*Raghuvamśā* 10.22). Kālidāsa supports the great position given to *Saguṇabrahman* by Viśiṣṭādvaita of Rāmānuja and Dvaita of Madhvā in creation.

In *Raghuvamśā*, Kālidāsa asks, "Who can know the true nature of the one who is not born, who takes birth, who has no desire, who destroys his enemies, who is asleep and who is awake (*Raghuvamśā* 10.24). The real devotee of Kālidāsa based on the philosophy of *Viṣṇu* can be seen here. The *Kumārasambhava* focuses on the unique nature of the immortal and magical creator. It describes you as also a father. That is what God is. Everyone else sees you as a part of it. It is the same with the *Vedasā* (*Kumārasambhava* 2.14).

In *Abhiñānaśākuntala*, Kālidāsa presents the creator in a very different way. It is the first creation of the creator. As fate would have it, the one who brought the *Havis*, the one who performed the *homa*, the one who spent time with the two (sun and moon), the one who is heard in the universe, and who is said to be the cause of all phenomena, is the one who is the soul of all things

(*Abhiñānaśākuntala* 1.1). Kālidāsa begins the play by wishing the audience the ultimate prosperity of self-reliance. Kālidāsa also explains in the *Vikramorvaśīya* that a single force controls the material universe. The same power (*śakti*) that the mokṣa seeks is referred to as a form of *Iśwara* (Śiva), the *Brahman*, the universal and the Vedānta, sought by the Rāmānuja and Madhvā (Vikramorvaśīyam. 1.1). Kālidāsa hopes that his steadfast devotion to the single power (*antaryāmi*), the embodiment of *mokṣa*, will give him *niśreyasa*.

The love enshrined in devotion can be seen in *Mālavikāgnimitra*. He wears clothes made of leather to gain wealth for his devotees. Though he shares half his body with his wife, he lives like an obsessed yogi. The Lord, who ruled the whole world with eight bodies, was never affected by pride (*Mālavikāgnimitra* 1.1). The *Bharatavākhyā* in *Abhiñānaśākuntala* is shared to the rebirth less thought. The king can rule the kingdom. The *Saraswati* mentioned in the *śruti*-s is worshipped. The sincere prayer moves devotees that the powerful and self-righteous *Nīllohita* should destroy his reincarnation (*Abhiñānaśākuntala* 7.35).

Śankara, who harmonised the emotional aspects of human culture with practical reality, explained that the spiritual reality is the non-dual *Brahman*. Rāmānuja, the founder of Viśiṣṭādvaita, clarified that valid means like perception, inference, and so on cannot explain the *Nirguṇabrahman* of Śankara. His concept of *Brahman* is different. He described the ultimate reality as *Iśwara* (*Viṣṇu*), endowed with knowledge, kindness, bliss and goodness. Madhvā's *Brahman* is an independent power where spirituality and the material world are the realities that depend on *Brahman*. He added that God creates all the universe's manifestations known by the different names of *Viṣṇu*, *Hari* and *Bhagāvan*.

Devotional worship is a speciality of Kālidāsa literature. He depicts the juxtaposition of Śiva and Pārvati embodied in the first verse of *Raghuvamśā*, which illustrates *ardhanārīśvara* concepts in early Hindu traditions as a journey to discover the true meaning of words. Kālidāsa says that just as the waters of the Ganges flow into the ocean, so do the paths of righteousness, which are divided in different ways among the *āgama*-s, flow into you (*Viṣṇu*) (*Raghuvamśā* 10.26).

The poets and thinkers of ancient India were skilful in poetically presenting the undercurrents of worldly experience. Kālidāsa, who gave simple and beautiful poetry to his fellow citizens, was a *Krāntadarśī* who integrated the thought processes inherent in Indian philosophy. Kālidāsa's quest for a visible power beyond the concept of God leads his followers to the non-dualistic Kālidāsa. The innovation of Vedic rituals was a speciality of medieval India. The decline of the Buddhist and Jain sects was the main reason for the changes in the field of knowledge. The approach that gave impetus to the change in Vedic culture was adopted by commentators such as Śankara, Rāmānuja and Madhvā in their interpretations of texts such as the *Brahmasūtra*, the *Upaniṣad*-s and the *Bhagavadgītā*. Both Viśiṣṭādvaita and Dvaita have accepted Vedānta as an expression of devotion and a philosophical reinterpretation of the Vedic tradition. (Damodaran K, 2015. 336) Vedic and Tantric concepts are aligned in several places in Kālidāsa's works. Kālidāsa contributed to Indian culture as an utterly independent vision either when Vedic philosophy was imprinted in different systems or much before that. Thus, Kālidāsa, who went beyond the poet to the philosopher, was a fellow-doer who embodied the Vedānta thoughts in poetry.

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